

1 **Phosphatase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: DUSP5.**

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6 Up to 50% of patients with HER2+ subtype breast cancer develop metastasis to the central nervous
7 system, most commonly the brain, demanding rapid therapeutic approaches to limit spread of the HER2+
8 primary tumor to distant sites (1-3). We recently described the existence of a group of genes that reside
9 proximal to *ERBB2* (the gene that encodes the human epidermal growth factor *HER2*) at 17q12: their
10 differential expression in HER2+ breast cancer, their up-regulation in HER2+ breast cancer, their
11 differential expression and up-regulation in central nervous system (CNS) metastasis and, based on
12 human survival studies, their function in supporting metastasis to the CNS, indicating that the predilection
13 of HER2+ patients to develop CNS metastasis was a phenomena attributable to the disease and not
14 HER2+-targeted therapies (4). Disease recurrence following disease remission (relapse), resistance to
15 trastuzumab or otherwise inadequate long-term control of disease are challenges that limit effectiveness of
16 existing HER2+-targeted therapies. We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (5, 6) to measure total
17 transcription in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer. We describe here one member
18 of a group of phosphatases up-regulated and differentially expressed in human HER2+ breast cancer,
19 DUSP5, as a catalytically available phosphatase and candidate therapeutic target for the prevention and
20 management of CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer.
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CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human HER2+ organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with HER2+ breast cancer with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in HER2+ disease with rapidity and ease. Management of major public health problems requires research (bench)-based management in the short run and long run (9). One example of such a major problem is CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer (10-13): this is a type of cancer that affects a human sex with relatively high frequency, a subtype of that cancer that is diagnosed in approximately one quarter of patients diagnosed with that cancer, and a specific complication of that subtype develops in half of affected patients.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through rigorous study of the HER2+ tumor transcriptome: a phosphatase target that is up-regulated, catalytically available and subtype-specific: DUSP5.

Results

Figure 1: DUSP5 is differentially expressed in HER2+ breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=11 normal breast tissue

n=30 primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
209457_at	3.50E-09	-7.43685	10.562846	-3.9217854	DUSP5	3592/29,873	88.0

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal breast tissue and in primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of dual specificity phosphatase 5, encoded by *DUSP5* in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of DUSP5 changed more than nearly 90% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of DUSP5 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of DUSP5 during transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the HER2+ breast cancer subtype.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=35 normal breast tissue

n=18 primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7930413	1.57E-02	-2.4937717	-3.8938714	-0.38269376	DUSP5	12072/33,297	63.7

1 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+
2 breast cancers relative to normal breast tissue, in a second microarray dataset (6) from independent
3 investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of DUSP5 in HER2+
4 breast cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of DUSP5 here changed more than nearly 65% of
5 the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured -
6 in this case, 33,297 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of
7 DUSP5 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of DUSP5 during
8 transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the HER2+ breast cancer subtype.

9 Thus, differential and increased expression of DUSP5 defines the transcriptional landscape of the
10 HER2+ breast cancer subtype in humans.

11 **Discussion**

12 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
13 treatment with a second treatment (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
14 trastuzumab). Small molecule inhibitors of DUSP5 phosphatase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety,
15 can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with HER2+ metastasis, with the goal of identifying the
16 most effective phosphatase inhibitors for management of HER2+ disease in humans and utilizing these
17 adjunctive phosphatase inhibitors early in disease to prevent rather than treat CNS disease. We recently
18 used primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple phosphatases that we deemed candidate
19 therapeutic targets in management of breast cancer, and fortuitously found their decreased expression
20 was specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients with HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A
21 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
22 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective
23 in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).
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Methods

We utilized GSE45827 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in HER2+ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer, as compared to normal breast (along with GSE87049 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).